

A UNIQUE REPRESENTATIVE OF PHILOSOPHICAL LYRICS IN OUR NATIONAL POETRY: H. JAVID

Mammadova Nushaba Mammadali gizi

Nakhchivan State University

Doctor of Philosophy in Philology, Associate Professor

Abstract

The article reflects H. Javid's humanism - his deep faith in man, his freedom and development. In his works, H. Javid criticizes the problems of society, the future of revolutions, and injustice. His dramas and lyric poems, especially such works as "Mother", "Sheikh Sanan", and "Khayyam", are the main expressions of his philosophical worldview. Huseyn Javid is unique because in his works he reflects the meaning of life, the mystery of the universe, the social and spiritual state of man, and existential questions. His poetry combines the enthusiasm of romanticism with the depth of his philosophical thought. The article touches on these issues.

Keywords: national poetry, philosophical lyrics, H. Javid, creative thought, drama, philosophical content etc.

Huseyn Javid is considered a unique representative of the Azerbaijani national poetry with his works rich in themes and ideas, reflecting philosophical lyrics, deep meanings of life, and secrets of the universe. Idealistic, romantic, and philosophical thoughts occupy a central place in his creativity, and in his works such as "Iblis" and "Sheikh Sanan", deep philosophical meanings are revealed based on great themes such as the struggle between man and the devil, the divine and the worldly, and good and evil. Although Huseyn Javid is mainly known for his drama and lyric poetry, all his work has a deep philosophical content; these works, such as "Mother", "Sheikh Sanan", "Uçurum", "Afət", "Khayyam", "Sayavuş", show himself by working on the ideas of man, society, life, death, spirituality, religious mysticism and freedom through dramas and poetry, and especially express his love of life and optimism, as in "Khayyam". His main philosophical dramas: "Mother" (1910) - about love of the homeland, the idea of the mother and social issues; "Sheikh Sanan" (1914) - about the philosophy of love and freedom against religious fanaticism; "Uçurum" (1919) - about the tragedies and spiritual crises of the human spirit; "Afət" (1922) - about the ideas of social inequality, revolution and progress; The works "Prophet", "Topal Teymur", "Knyaz" are about historical and social themes; "Khayyam" (1922) - a dialogue with the spirit of Omar Khayyam, the meaning of life, optimism; "Sayavuş" - works about spirituality, power, justice and the fate of the people. Mystical elements (Iblis, spirits), symbolic images are widely used in his works (for example, Sheikh Sanan). Especially in "Khayyam" and his later works, there is a belief in life and rebirth. The immortality of the soul, the inner world of man are among his main themes.

in "Iblis" and Teymur in "Topal Teymur" carry symbolic meanings and raise broader philosophical issues. Huseyn Javid, for the first time in Azerbaijani poetry, wrote great tragedies on topics such as "Iblis" and "Sheikh Sanan", contributing to the enrichment of national literature with global philosophical themes. Thus, Huseyn Javid constitutes one of the points of philosophical lyrics in our national poetry, and his works leave a deep mark in this field.

He defended that the power that will save the world is spiritual purity and love. The glorification of

human beauty, love for people, contrasts between personality and time, human sorrow, etc. are among the main issues in Javid's lyrics. Sufism (Sufi) ideas in the work of Huseyn Javid divine love, human-universe unity, the return of the soul to its divine origin, and pantheistic views As a "poet of the heavens", the poet glorified spiritual ascension, the restraint of the soul, and the search for truth within man, turning his philosophical and mystical views into the focus of his works. Javid combines Sufism with active human perfection, humanism and high moral values, rather than passive mysticism. Professor Gulshan Aliyeva-Kangarli, Doctor of Philology, who calls Sufism the most perfect philosophical movement, refers to the philosophy of Huseyn Javid in her article "The Mystical Layer of Romantic Tragedy" and comes to the following conclusion about the great thinker-poet: he "was a Sufi before becoming a romantic" (7, p. 26). She sees Sufi ideas in many places in the work "Sheikh Sanan" and confirms this with examples from the work and quotes from other researchers. Doctor of Philology Nazima Akhundova saw Sufi ideas in the play "Sheikh Sanan" and compared H. Javid's work in this work with Mansur Hallaj Miyanechi and M. Fuzuli (1, p. 6).

Many research works note that Javid was a Sufi before becoming a romantic poet. The ideas of the integrity of the universe, the spiritual unity of man with God occupy an important place in his lyrics. The motifs of man's spiritual purification through the attainment of absolute beauty (God) are presented at the junction of classical Eastern philosophy and modern romanticism. For Javid, national identity is a part of humanity. His philosophy "Turan needs love, not a sword" saw national revival in spiritual upliftment and science. He brought a new rhythm, form and intellectual depth to Azerbaijani poetry. Javid's lyrics are not just an expression of emotions, but a manifesto of the "Thinking Soul". While still living in Germany, his close acquaintance with European philosophical thought (Hoete, Schiller) allowed him to combine Eastern wisdom with Western rationalism in his work.

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